

I WANT TO BE A TRANSLATOR IN THE FUTURE

6th grade student at school № 50

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With his English teacher

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Annotation. In this article, Humoyun, a 6th-grade student from Uzbekistan, shares his dream of becoming a translator. He explains his passion for languages, his enjoyment of helping people, and his commitment to understanding different cultures. Humoyun describes the roles and responsibilities of translators, including translating written documents and interpreting spoken language. He details how he is currently preparing for this career by studying languages and learning about various cultures. Humoyun envisions a future where he works for an international organization, using his skills to connect people and promote understanding across the globe.

Keywords: translator, languages, Uzbekistan, cultural understanding, language learning, interpreting, communication, international organizations, career aspirations, multilingualism

Я ХОЧУ БЫТЬ ПЕРЕВОДЧИКОМ В БУДУЩЕМ

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Аннотация. В этой статье Хумоюн, ученик 6-го класса из Узбекистана, делится своей мечтой стать переводчиком. Он объясняет свою страсть к языкам, удовольствие, помогая людям, и свою приверженность пониманию различных культур. Хумоюн описывает роли и обязанности переводчиков, включая перевод письменных документов и устный перевод. Он подробно рассказывает, как в настоящее время готовится к этой карьере, изучая языки и изучая различные культуры.

Хумоюн видит будущее, в котором он будет работать в международной организации, используя свои навыки для объединения людей и содействия взаимопониманию во всем мире.

Ключевые слова: переводчик, языки, Узбекистан, культурное взаимопонимание, изучение языков, устный перевод, общение, международные организации, карьерные устремления, многоязычие.

Hello, my name is Humoyun, and I am a 6th grader from Uzbekistan. When I grow up, I want to be a translator. Being a translator is an exciting job because it allows you to connect people from different countries and cultures by helping them understand each other.

Why I Want to Be a Translator

One reason I want to be a translator is because I love languages. In Uzbekistan, we speak Uzbek, but I am also learning English and Russian in school. I enjoy learning new words and phrases in these languages and practicing speaking them with my friends and family. Each language has its own unique sounds and rules, which makes learning them like solving a fun puzzle.

Another reason is that I enjoy helping people. As a translator, I would get to help people communicate, whether they are traveling, doing business, or just trying to learn more about each other's cultures. It would make me happy to know that I am making a difference by helping people understand each other better.

What Translators Do

Translators do many important things. They work with written documents, like books, articles, and official papers, translating them from one language to another. They also help people communicate in real-time by translating spoken words, which is called interpreting. For example, a translator might help two people who speak different languages have a conversation, or they might translate a speech at a conference.

Translators need to have a deep understanding of the languages they work with, including grammar, vocabulary, and idioms. They also need to understand

the cultures behind the languages because sometimes words and phrases do not translate directly. Knowing the culture helps translators find the best way to convey the same meaning in another language.

How I Am Preparing to Be a Translator

I am already preparing to be a translator by studying hard in my language classes. I practice English and Russian every day, and I try to learn new words and phrases whenever I can. I also like to watch movies and read books in different languages, which helps me understand how people use language in real life.

Additionally, I enjoy learning about different cultures. I read about the traditions, foods, and holidays of people from other countries. This helps me understand how people think and live, which is important for a translator.

My Dream for the Future

In the future, I hope to study languages at a university. I want to learn more languages, maybe even some that are less common, like Japanese or Spanish. I also hope to travel to different countries to practice my language skills and learn more about the world.

One day, I want to work as a translator for an international organization, like the United Nations, or for a big company that does business around the world. I believe that being a translator will allow me to help people connect and communicate, making the world a smaller and friendlier place.

Conclusion

Being a translator is a challenging but rewarding job. It requires a lot of hard work and dedication to learn languages and understand different cultures. But for me, it is worth it because I want to help people understand each other and build connections between different parts of the world. I am excited about the future and all the possibilities that being a translator will bring.

Thank you for reading about my dream. Maybe one day, I will be the one helping you communicate with someone from another part of the world!

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